

LEXICOGRAPHIC EXPRESSION OF POLITENESS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Dilrabo Nazirqulova Zafariddin qizi
Abduvahobova Mahina Ozodxonovna

Scientific advisor

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Annotation: this thesis is about the lexicographic expression of politeness in the English language. There are given some explanations and descriptions of politeness and its equivalents in the language.

Key words: lexicographic, politeness, definition, dictionary, concept, English, language.

The consideration of the lexicographic expression of politeness requires looking through some definitions of several dictionaries in English. Analyzing how the concept of politeness is presented in the English dictionaries, we will proceed from the fact that the data of explanatory dictionaries, in addition to providing reliable and objective information about the semantics of a word, also “can be considered as an adequate reflection of the dominant culture” [Slyshkin, 1996].

American explanatory dictionaries define ‘polite’ as:

- I. “refined, mannerly and courteous”
- II. 1. “polished; cultured; refined, correct”
2. “having good manners; courteous”

The etymology of the word given in the same place is indicated as *polite* comes from the Latin *politus* pp from the verb *polire-to polite, that is polish, grind*. Hence, the conclusion is that, politeness and good manners are developed through the result of repeated “*polishing*”, training.

Merriem-Webster dictionary and thesaurus of English (1828) defines the word *polite* as such:

1. a :of relating to, or having the characteristics of advanced culture
b :marked by refined cultural interests and pursuits especially in arts and belles lettres
2. a :showing or characterized by correct social usage,
b :marked by an appearance of consideration, tact, deference, or courtesy,
c :marked by a lack of roughness or crudities.

The history and etymology of the word in the same dictionary are given as the word *polite* come from Middle English (Scots) *polit*, Latin *politus*, from past participle of *polire*. First known use of the word “*polite*” is about 1500c., in the meaning of, relating to, or having the characteristics of advanced culture.

American Dictionary of Problem words and Phrases G. Shaw (DPWE) analyzes the synonyms of *polite* and *courteous*. *Polite* serves to characterize a well-mannered person, who is able to behave themselves in any situations, a civilized person, aspiring to avoid conflict: “A *polite* person shows good manners towards others in his speech and actions; he is well bred and gracious. A *polite* individual avoids being rude as a result and because he is aware of the demands and requirements of civil manners.” *Courteous*, on the other hand, characterizes a person, consciously showing a kind, balanced, dignified and respectful attitude towards other people: “A *courteous* person is not only *polite*; he makes an active effort to be kindly, graceful, dignified and poised.” In most cases these words are interchangeable, but the

dictionary directly indicates the difference in their meanings: polite serves to reflect only the external, etiquette side of the phenomenon, while courteous conveys a fundamentally different-kind and respectful attitude towards a partner on communication: “In most instances, the two words are interchangeable, but courteous is a stronger word than *polite* and suggests a fundamental attitude towards others, whereas *polite* relates to surface manners only: It is polite to say “*Good morning*” to someone; it is *courteous* to treat others with respect and kindness”. According to the observations of V.I. Karasik on this occasion: “Politeness in its essence is a manifestation of respect to another person”. The definition of politeness as good manners emphasizes the procedural side (behavioral, outer plan) of this phenomenon. The external side of the phenomenon is to a certain extent autonomous, and therefore, good manners can be combined with low intentions and lack of respect for the person. This internal tension in the understanding of the concept “politeness” find its lexical expression in English like this: “*polite*”- “*muloyim*”, and *courteous-xushmuomala, odobli* differ in that the first word more denotes the external aspect of behavior, and the second word denotes the external manifestation and internal good disposition towards the man”[Karasik,2002].

Analyzing the material of American lexicographic sources, gave us the following conclusions:

- 1)the invariant meaning of the analyzed synonyms polite and courteous is the observance of *décorum*,the ability to behave, understood as a sign of the culture acquired training (“a result of training”);
- 2)The difference between synonyms can be traced along the vector: polite-courteous(politeness+respect), *muloyim-baadab(xushmuomalalik+hurmat)*
- 3)Ambivalency of the concepts in the dictionaries is not given, and the derivatives of the concepts are not found.(WNWD)

Let’s consider the meaning of the lexeme “polite” on the material of British explanatory dictionaries. British explanatory dictionaries define polite as:

- 1) “behaving in a way that is socially correct and shows understanding of and care for other people’s feelings”(CDOE)
- 2) “someone who is polite has good manners and behaves in away that is socially correct and not rude to other people”(Collins dictionary)

In the material of Longman Dictionary of Modern English, (LDCE) listed four meanings of the word “polite”

- 1) “behaving and speaking in a way that is correct for the social situation you are in, and showing that you are careful to consider other people’s needs and feelings”
- 2) observing the norms of secular behavior, etiquette norms, accepted in the society: “you make polite conversation, remarks, etc because it is considered socially correct to do this: a few polite remarks about the weather”;
- 3) as the synonym of the words *cultured, civilized* in the phrases *polite society,polite circle, polite company* and often with the meaning of a humor;
- 4) having the external norms and rules of behavior, often hiding their inner true feelings: “just/only being polite-saying something you may not really believe”

In this dictionary(LDCE), the word polite given as the synonymous with the words *well mannered, well-behaved, courteous,respectful, deferential* and *civil*.

It should be noted, that, the definition of “*politeness*” is not given in any English explanatory dictionaries, it is only indicated as the derivation of the noun made from the adjective “*polite*” and also, the derivatives of the word “*polite*” are also absent in the language.

Analyzing British explanatory dictionaries gave us the following conclusions:

- 1) invariant meaning of the concept “*polite*” is expressed as “well-mannered, respecting oneself and others” and the social significance of correct behavior (socially correct) is dominated;
- 2) the ambivalent nature is inherent in this concept is fixed at the level of dictionary definitions and finds lexical expression in the synonymous pair *polite-courteous*;
- 3) the derivative of *polite* in the given explanatory dictionaries are not given;

Thus, although, the concept of politeness is considered as “showing the respect to other people”, this concept in English is characterized by the internal tension. Nevertheless, we can reduce the common features of the studied words, to the following elementary meanings and semantic components that make the structure of the meaning:

- 1) human behavior;
- 2) a positive attitude of a person to another one;
- 3) the demonstration of this relationship with the help of accepted verbal and non-verbal ways of expression.

So, in the English language, the concept of politeness is expressed with the help of two basic lexical units, the relationship of which is characterized by the nature of semantic similarity: *polite-courteous*(*muloyim-xushxulq*). Therefore, it should be singled out in the English language, that, on the one hand, the semantic connection between politeness and etiquette, demonstrating good manners(although not always sincere), and on the other hand, the connection of politeness and self-esteem, as well as tact.

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